

The role of communication networks in adoption of sustainable innovations: the case of BIM

João Gonçalves, Jorge Pereira Campos, Jason Pridmore, Yijing Wang¹

¹Department of Media and Communication, Erasmus University Rotterdam, NL

Communication practices related to organizational contexts pose critical potential and limitations for resolving issues of significant concern. The construction industry currently faces some of the most impactful and pivotal issues on a European scale. More than a fifth of all European workplace fatal accidents took place in the construction industry (*Accidents at Work Statistics*, 2022). Furthermore, construction is responsible for a third of the world's waste and more than 40% of worldwide CO² emissions (*Construction and Demolition Waste*, 2018). Faced with these significant challenges, industry and policy makers see new digital technologies providing answers to a number of these. Specifically, Building Information Modelling (BIM), has shown promise in accident reduction (Yuan et al., 2019) and significant use more effective low carbon emission design of buildings (Yang et al., 2018). However, resistance to change was identified as the key barrier for adoption of BIM and other digital technologies, and communication was identified as a primary aspect to improve these circumstances (Olawumi et al., 2018).

This project aims to identify the role of networks and digital communication channels as keyways to overcome barriers to BIM adoption. BIM follows trends for digitalization and datafication in other fields, by enabling new ways of communication between the many stakeholders involved in a construction project, by effectively creating a digital model of the building and the construction project. We focus not only on BIM as an ICT, but also in the ways in which ICTs such as social media and may facilitate the diffusion of high-impact technological innovations such as BIM. We also hope that this project will constitute a case study for ways in which communication scholars can engage with other scientific and technical fields to study the diffusion of innovative technologies through digital channels. We have conducted a survey with European participants from the architecture, construction, and engineering (ACE) industry to assess BIM adoption and to what extent it is determined by communication channels and external drivers.

Theory and context

BIM technology

BIM is a technology that allows for the digital representation of the physical and functional characteristic of a building or infrastructure. It is a platform that allows various construction-industry stakeholders to access and collaborate on a single platform, thus simplifying collaboration amongst stakeholders and organization of the construction process. This technology is crucial not only during the design and construction phase, but also throughout the building's lifecycle. BIM technologies improve an accurate representation of a buildings' design which may help with its construction and future renovations, they aid collaboration between stakeholders (e.g., architects, engineers, contractors), improves decision-making as workers are able to predict potential outcomes based on the digital representation of buildings, and improves sustainability by reducing waste.

While the benefits of BIM have been widely documented, underestimating the process leading to its adoption has led to its outcomes not being fully realized (Wang & Song, 2017). BIM

adoption varies considerably depending on country context, reaching percentages up to 79% in the United States and as low as 23% in Poland (Ullah et al., 2019). This highlights the role that cultural and policy dimensions have in determining BIM adoption. Despite the role of these dimensions, organizational factors, including communication about BIM, also play a key role in determining adoption (Abbasnejad et al., 2021).

Diffusion of innovation

The diffusion of innovation model (Rogers, 1962) provides a useful framework to assess the status of BIM adoption within the construction sector and the main factors conditioning this adoption. According to diffusion of innovation, there are multiple categories of adopters for a given innovation, and the rate of adoption and success of an innovation largely depends on the communication channels through which this innovation spreads. While the innovation itself is one of the key aspects that Rogers identified in determining innovation adoption, this model highlights how other, non-technical, factors may be highly influential in the success of a new idea or technology. In the case of BIM, this underlines the importance of looking beyond the technical aspects of BIM and examining the communication channels and dynamics that surround its diffusion.

When studying the diffusion of an innovation within a specific industrial sector, such as construction, one must acknowledge and consider the specific features of this sector. In particular, the construction sector has been known to be a laggard in the adoption of digital innovations. This is likely due to the complexity and high number of stakeholders involved in construction projects, which make the construction industry particularly prone to resistance to change. Furthermore, a substantial part of the construction sector, particularly in Europe where this study takes place, is comprised of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which are less prone to adopt innovations at early stages because they do not have financial resources to take risk and deal with the consequences of unsuccessful innovations.

Valente & Davis (1999) argue that most of diffusion of innovation studies are retrospective and have not collected information on interpersonal communications networks. This is also the case for studies which incorporate the diffusion of innovation theory to study BIM adoption, which focus on potential barriers for adoption but disregard the role that interpersonal networks have in overcoming these barriers (Karampour et al., 2021; Shirowzhan et al., 2020). They present a method for accelerate the diffusion of innovations using opinion leaders. Opinion leaders are individuals or organizations that can influence other individuals' attitudes and behaviors in their communication network (Rogers, 2003; Cho, Hwang, & Lee, 2012).

Given that opinion leaders have the potential to cause behavioral change among innovation adopters, we posit that:

H1: Increased reliance on interpersonal networks for information about technological innovations is positively related with BIM adoption.

In addition, considering that company size has an impact on the rate of innovation adoption (Askarany & Smith, 2008), we expect the effect of H1 to be moderated by size:

H2: The positive effect of reliance on interpersonal networks on BIM adoption is moderated by company size such that the effect will be weaker for SMEs than for larger companies.

Social influence

When considering the role that communication channels, including interpersonal networks, may have in the diffusion of innovations, the literature on Social Influence (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004) may prove to be useful. While social influence as concept is sometimes used in studies of diffusion of innovations (Deroian, 2002), it is often employed as an analytical construct in the scope of social network analysis to describe the most influential nodes in a social network graph (Kempe et al., 2005).

We aim to go beyond the analytical usage of social influence to draw from its theoretical potential as an explanatory factor for diffusion of innovations. In this scope, we argue that there are two key paths in which digital communication may enhance BIM adoption: (1) perceptions of adoption, following the standard patterns of diffusion of innovations, will lead to phenomena of conformity and boost BIM usage through a “fear of missing out”. (2) Endorsement of BIM technologies by key influential actors in the construction sector (opinion leaders) which will lead to phenomena of compliance and boost BIM usage through social desirability mechanisms.

Conformity consists of adjusting one’s behavior according to the perceived behavior of others to achieve goals of accuracy (perform a task in the best possible way) and affiliation (gain or maintain membership in a group) (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004). In the case of BIM, when companies perceive that their competitors adopting BIM, they may feel increased competitive pressure to adopt the technology themselves. Conversely, if they perceive that their collaborators and peers are shifting towards BIM, they may fear losing affiliation and connections with that particular group of stakeholders.

Conformity effects may also be useful in explaining how perceived adoption, rather than actual adoption, may mitigate resistance to change within the industry, especially among small and medium enterprises. Specifically, when BIM is communicated through institutional channels, such as news websites dedicated to construction or trade association newsletters, this may signal widespread adoption to readers and trigger phenomena of social influence through conformity. We therefore hypothesize that:

H3: Getting information about innovations from institutional channels is related to an increase in perceived competitive pressure.

Given that conformity is also guided by goals of accuracy, we also expect information on institutional channels to foster the belief that BIM brings more benefits than costs, therefore:

H4: Getting information about innovations from institutional channels is related to an increase in the perceived benefits versus costs of BIM.

While conformity may be one of the key social influence factors leading to BIM adoption, phenomena of compliance should also be considered. Compliance consists of a behavioural change prompted by a request from the influencing party. This request may be explicit, but it is also often implicit, e.g., when an expert presents and discusses the benefits of BIM adoption within the construction industry (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004). Compliance directly connects with the role of opinion leaders within the diffusion of innovation models. Interpersonal communications do not necessarily shift one’s estimate of how many companies are adopting a specific innovation, but it may lead individuals to comply with a request or nudge to adopt that innovation.

Like conformity, compliance is also guided by goals of accuracy. This means that influence through interpersonal networks may also lead individuals to shift their perceptions of the benefits of BIM technology in a positive way.

H5: Getting information about innovations from interpersonal channels is related to an increase in the perceived benefits versus costs of BIM.

When considering the role of communication practices in diffusion of innovation, one must account for the role that social media play in terms of social influence. While they are not necessarily the only or main channel through which individuals receive information about innovations, social media still play a relevant role in terms of fostering adoption (Masele & Rwehikiza, 2022). Considering that social media blend mass and traditional communication with interpersonal communication (Neubaum & Krämer, 2017), we expect these channels to have an effect on both drivers of BIM adoption:

H6: Getting information about innovations from social media channels is related to an increase in perceived competitive pressure.

H7: Getting information about innovations from social media channels is related to an increase in the perceived benefits versus costs of BIM.

Methods

To study the association between communication channels and BIM adoption we rely on a survey approach. While this limits our ability to draw causal conclusions from the data, it is more likely to allow us to reach the specific population of architecture, construction and engineering professionals that we are targeting. Qualitative research data collection methods require more time and investment from participants, and do not allow us to generalize results, which makes them less suitable for our research goal. In turn, experiments and longitudinal studies impose more requirements both in terms of participation time and ethical dimensions, therefore not being a feasible approach to for industry professions in the scope.

Sampling

This research project is embedded in an EU funded Horizon project¹, and we have relied on construction organizations that were members of this project to disseminate the survey among their members and through social media. While convenience sampling limits the generalizability of results, it was the only way to feasibly reach the specific sample we were targeting. The survey distributed in December 2020, a total of 877 participants were reached through these methods, of which 269 completed the survey. These respondents came from a total of 24 European countries with most replies coming from Bulgaria (19.7%), Spain (12.6%), Italy (12.6%), France (8.6%), Hungary (7.1%), and Germany (5.6%), while more than 80% of participants were SMEs. Given that there were personal channels involved in the dissemination of the survey and that the population itself is quite restrict, demographic information was not collected to protect participant privacy.

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The sample in terms of company size are as follows: < 10 employees – 37.1% of participants; < 50 employees – 29.1% of participants; < 250 employees – 15.6% of participants; >250 of employees – 18.2% of participants. Most participants work in organizations from the construction sector (30.0%), followed by architecture (18.5%) and structural engineering (13.5%). All participants gave their consent to the study in the beginning of the survey. They also provided their email address to receive follow-up information, which was then removed from the dataset for analysis, but also allowed participants to withdraw their data from the study if desired.

A second wave of the study was sent to 163 participants who consented being contacted for this purpose. The purpose of this wave was to assess longitudinal effects and establish causal relationships. However, a high attrition with only 23 fully completed surveys meant that we are underpowered to test this type of effects in the scope of this project.

Measures

The wave 1 survey measured the main barriers and external drivers for BIM adoption, BIM usage, main communication channels for BIM information, main influential actors for BIM information, presence of BIM champions within an organisation, as well as basic information about the participants' company and profile. The key variables of use of this paper are presented below:

Communication channels

Participants were asked in the survey about the influence of 10 different communication channels on their decisions to engage with digital innovations. They could answer in a five-point scale with options ranging from "Very uninfluential" to "Very influential". Channels included on the list were decided upon by the research team after consultation with experts in BIM. To assess if items would cluster in the different channel types, we conducted principal component analysis with VARIMAX rotation [KMO = .74, Bartlett's test of sphericity $X^2(45) = 790.69, p < .001$]. Three factors were selected with eigenvalues higher than one. The factors, their factor loadings and reliability statistics are presented below in Table 1.

Table 1: *Pattern matrix for communication channels PCA*

	Component		
	Institutional	Interpersonal	Social Media
TV	0,88		
Radio	0,85		
Newspaper	0,82		
Conferences and presentations		0,78	
Face-to-face conversation my network		0,76	
Conversation with consultants		0,76	
Linked In			0,81
Twitter			0,79

Internet forums		0,46	0,63
Blogs		0,43	0,62
% Variance explained	33.9%	20.0%	12.6%
Cronbach's α	.82	.71	.75
Mean (SD)	2.17 (1.10)	3.94 (0.84)	2.96 (1.04)

Competitive pressure

Competitive pressure was measured with a single item stating that competitive pressure is a driver for BIM adoption ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 1.10$). The five answer options ranged from *Strongly Disagree* to *Strongly Agree*.

Benefits and costs of BIM

A scale measuring the perceived benefits and costs from BIM was constructed from a broader 22 item measure concerning the barriers for BIM adoption. PCA component analysis [KMO = .85, Bartlett's test of sphericity $X^2(231) = 2827.14$, $p < .001$] with varimax rotation extracted a total of 5 factors with eigenvalues higher than one, of which the first was composed of the items: "BIM is too complex and takes too long to get up to speed", "BIM technologies are not user friendly", "Uncertain Return on Investment", "BIM is not relevant for the projects we work on", "High investment needed in software and training", "Incompatibility of different software packages". The resulting scale is reliable with a Cronbach's α of .78 ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 0.88$).

Company size

Company size was measured by asking participants about the number of employees in a company. Companies reporting less than 250 employees were labelled as SMEs (82.1%), while companies with at least 250 employees were labelled large (17.9%), following the threshold of the European Commission's definition for SMEs.

BIM Usage

BIM usage was assessed with a self-reported measure asking participants if their company is involved in BIM projects, with 36.7% of participants saying no, while the remaining answered affirmatively.

Results

H1 and H2 posited that obtaining information about digital innovations through interpersonal networks would lead to greater BIM adoption, and that this effect would be moderated by company size. These hypotheses were tested through a logistic regression with BIM usage as the dependent variable, and reliance on interpersonal networks for digital innovation, company size, and an interaction term between these variables as independent variables. The model as a whole was found not to be significant $X^2(3) = 2.59$, $p = .459$, Nagelkerke $R^2 = .02$. Therefore, both H1 and H2 are rejected, BIM adoption is not related to use of interpersonal channels for information about innovations.

The next stage of analysis tests which information channels are associated with an increased perception of competitive pressure. We conducted a linear regression with perceptions of competitive pressure as the independent variable, and personal channels, institutional channels (H3) and social media channels (H6) as independent variables. The model was significant $F(3,241) = 2.92$, $p = .035$, with the three variables explaining 3.5% of the variation in perceived competitive pressure. Institutional ($\beta = .03$, $p = .699$) and interpersonal ($\beta = .03$, $p = .637$) were not significant predictors of competitive pressure, thus rejecting H3. Social media channels were a significant positive predictor of perceived competitive pressure ($\beta = .16$, $p = .022$), therefore supporting H6.

To test hypotheses related to perceptions of benefits and costs of BIM, a linear regression was conducted with this variable as the dependent variable, and institutional (H4), interpersonal (H5) and social media (H7) channels as independent variables. The model was significant $F(3,245) = 2.90$, $p = .036$, with the three variables explaining 3.5% of the variation in perceived benefits and costs of BIM. Interpersonal channels did not have a significant influence on perceptions of BIM benefits and costs ($\beta = -.05$, $p = .438$), thus rejecting H5. Institutional channels had a significant positive effect on perceptions of BIM ($\beta = .13$, $p = .040$). However, this effect is in the opposite direction to what we expected. Since the scale is reverse, higher values mean that participants see more barriers to BIM adoption, which in this case means that participants who follow institutional channels tend to perceive more barriers to BIM, contrary to what we hypothesised in H4. Finally, social media channels have a marginally significant negative effect on perceptions of BIM ($\beta = -.14$, $p = .056$), meaning that there is partial support for H7, but still technically in the rejection threshold for a two-tailed distribution.

Discussion

Our study set out to examine the role that communication channels have in the diffusion of BIM technologies through a survey. Our first finding indicates that BIM adoption is not influenced by interpersonal channels. This may be because communication may be an important factor to stimulate interest in innovations, but actual innovation decisions then rely on economic factors first and foremost (Kutter et al., 2011). However, a competing explanation, also based on our broader results, is that the relevance of interpersonal communications for innovation adoption may be fading, since we found no significant effects of this variable in any of our outcomes.

In contrast with the role of interpersonal channels, social media channels appeared as key variable in explaining variance in perceived competitive pressure and, potentially, in perceptions of BIM technology. Based on these results, we believe that the lack of significance of interpersonal channels does not signal a lack of influence of figures such as opinion leaders in the diffusion of innovations, but rather a shift in the type of channels that these opinion leaders use to communicate. Social influence regarding BIM no longer happens in physical settings such as conferences and face-to-face meetings, but on social media sites such as LinkedIn, Twitter and Blogs. The relevance of social media is supported by the acceptance of H6 and partial support of H7, meaning that practitioners invested in BIM adoption should focus on these communication channels. However, it should be noted that this finding may not generalize to other innovation types. BIM is first and foremost a digital technology-based innovation, so it may be that individuals who are more prone to using digital communication channels are also more predisposed to its adoption. Because our research design does not allow us to test causality, we suggest that future studies in the diffusion of digital technologies tackle this issue.

Finally, findings regarding institutional channels seem counterintuitive when considering what we might expect to theory. However, this counterintuitive aspect can be somewhat understood when we dive into the actual media that constitute our understanding of institutional channels. Television, radio, and newspaper can be seen as legacy, and therefore less digital, communication channels. Therefor it is reasonable to assume that individuals who are prone to learning about innovations through these channels are less inclined to engage with digital innovations. Again, future research may play a relevant role in untangling the causal relationship between these aspects.

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